

**The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize For Modern Leaders
(The Rizal Prize/The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize)**
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Abstract

The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize for Modern Leaders is a proposal by Dexter P. Bano Jr. that aims to honor individuals who exhibit expertise, dedication, measurable impact, and years of proven track record in areas that Dr. Jose Rizal excelled in. The prize will be awarded to 24 laureates annually, representing the 24 students of Rizal in Dapitan, from 19 countries that Rizal visited during his lifetime. Nominations and laureates will be chosen from six categories: Science/Research/Engineering, Social enterprise/Philanthropy, Education, Medicine, Journalism/Literature/Arts, and Environment/Environmental Science. A special committee called The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee will be in charge of selecting the laureates, composed of Rizalian scholars, academics, civil society members, activists, leaders, members of the Order of the Knights of Rizal and The Rizal Academy for Innovation and Leadership, and living descendants of Dr. Jose Rizal. The committee will adhere to a vow of secrecy for 35 years and will sign for five years of service, adhering to Rizal's age when he could already read and write. If the 35-year vow of secrecy is violated, the responsible member/members will be dismissed, and the Order of the Knights of Rizal will start Operation Bagumbayan, a process of selecting a new committee. The proposal seeks to honor and recognize the legacy of Dr. Jose Rizal and inspire modern leaders to strive for excellence in their respective fields.

I. Number of Laureates

Twenty-four (24) Laureates annually will be chosen from the countries that Rizal visited during his lifetime including the Philippines. This number of laureates represents the twenty-four students of Rizal in Dapitan.

II. Areas and Fields

Nominations and laureates shall come from the areas that Rizal excelled. Laureates should exhibit expertise, dedication, measurable impact, and years of proven track record for the category that they will be nominated.

- The Rizal Prize for Science/Research/Engineering (4)
- The Rizal Prize for Social enterprise/Philanthropy (4)
- The Rizal Prize for Education (4)
- The Rizal Prize for Medicine (4)
- The Rizal Prize for Journalism/Literature/Arts (4)
- The Rizal Prize for Environment/Environmental Science (4)

III. Participating Countries

Nominations from nineteen (19) countries will be accepted and considered for the prize. Dr. Jose Rizal visited the following countries during his lifetime. These 19 participating countries also represent the day of his birthday.

- The Philippines
- Italy
- Spain
- France
- Germany
- Vietnam
- Sri Lanka
- Singapore
- Egypt
- Yemen
- Austria
- Czech Republic
- Switzerland
- China
- United States of America
- England
- Belgium
- Japan
- Africa

IV. Considerations, Nominations, and Selection

The Jury

- A jury composed of Rizalian scholars, academics, civil society members, activists, leaders, members of the Order of the Knights of Rizal and The Rizal Academy for Innovation and Leadership, and living descendants of Dr. Jose Rizal will be in-charge of the selection of laureates. This special committee shall be called **The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee (The Committee)**.
- Individuals who can be considered as active politicians, serving or running and those who are working for a politician cannot be a member of The Committee. Any member who has plans to run or work for any public political office in any country shall be dismissed and replaced.
- The members of The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee will have no capacity to submit nominations but they have the power to review all nominations and select the laureates.
- The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee will be composed of the following positions:

1. **Researchers (2)** – They are in-charge with anything to do with investigating and conducting due diligence to nominees.
 2. **Keyholders (2)** – They are the vault keepers. They also collate all the documents and files related to nominations up to the official announcement.
 3. **Communicators (2)** – They are in-charge with the delivery of announcements and letters for the entire duration of the nomination, selection, and official announcement.
 4. **Adjudicators (3)** – They are considered to be the peacekeepers of The Committee. They ensure resolution and proper consideration for all parties involved in any dispute. They will also bear “The Book” which will contain the names of those who sworn/will swear under the thirty-five (35) years vow of secrecy.
 5. **Notesworthy (2)** – They are the secretaries of The Committee. They provide documentation and notes keeping for the entire process, meetings, and events.
 6. **Gatekeepers (2)** – They secure the funds/finances of The Committee. They have the financial and accounting expertise.
 7. **Academician (3)** – They provide scholarly views for The Committee especially with regards to nomination and selection of laureates.
- The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee will sign and swear for five (5) years of service, the age of Rizal when he could already read and write.
 - The Committee will also adhere to vow of secrecy restricting them from publicizing and disclosing their membership and involvement for thirty-five (35) years, the age of Dr. Jose Rizal when he died.
 - During the fourth (4th) year of The Committee, they need to choose candidates to replace them for the next term. An online portal will also remain open for jury application.

After finalizing a list, the Communicators will send official invitations to the next possible members of The Committee. The candidates will swear to the 35-year vow of secrecy before being interviewed and deliberated. The Committee will then vote for the incoming members of the jury. The incoming members of The Committee will be invited and briefed.

- In any case of fortuitous event and proven incapacity to perform duties as a member, The Committee will choose a replacement from the eligible nominators. The new member will undergo the same process of secrecy and will serve only for the remaining period of tenure.
- If the thirty-five (35) year of secrecy gets violated, The Committee will automatically dismiss the responsible member/members. If The Committee violated this rule as an entity, the Order of the Knights of Rizal will start the “**Operation Bagumbayan**,” an event that should only be called to form The Committee.

Operation Bagumbayan

1. This will serve as the name of the process of selecting the inaugural jury.
2. The Supreme Council of the Order of the Knights of Rizal can only call this. They will send an announcement of jury application to all chapters around the world.
3. The Supreme Council of the Order of the Knights of Rizal will then convene with The Rizal Academy for Innovation and Leadership for the formation of a “Standing Group” composed of seven (individuals) for the purpose of receiving jury applications and selecting the members of the new/inaugural jury.
4. The inaugural jury will be called “**The First Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee**” which will then be named “The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee” after the first five (5) years of the prize.
5. This will serve as the name for the process of forestalling any possible damage in The Committee caused by any collective violation to the vow of secrecy.
6. The individuals involved will swear to the same thirty-five (35) years of secrecy.

The First Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee (The Inaugural Jury)

1. The Standing Group after swearing to the 35-year vow of secrecy will then start receiving and reviewing jury applications.
2. The Standing Group can send invitations letters (if necessary) to possible candidates for jury membership but it must be signed only as the following:

The Standing Group The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee

3. Within sixty (60) days after the deadline of submission, The Standing Group will then select the members of The First Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee through majority votes. A notification and invitation will be sent to each member and they will be invited to sign, to take oath, and to be briefed.
4. The members of The Committee must immediately report for duty after The Standing Group has withdrawn their responsibilities. The Committee will function independently.

Eligible Nominators

The Committee will not disclose the Eligible Nominators to the public. Invitations to nominate can only be supplied by The Committee.

The following are qualified as nominators:

- A. Members of the governments from the 19 participating countries
- B. Members of the United Nations
- C. Members of the Court of Justice from 19 participating countries

- D. Members of the embassies and ambassadors from 19 participating countries
- E. Members of the World Bank
- F. Members of the International Committee of the Red Cross
- G. Members of the International Monetary Fund
- H. Members of the Paris Peace Forum
- I. Members of the Freemasons
- J. Members of the Order of the Knights of Rizal and its affiliated organizations
- K. Members of the Rotary Clubs from 19 participating countries
- L. Members of international think tanks especially those from 19 participating countries
- M. Members of Chambers of Commerce from 19 participating countries
- N. Faculty members of universities and schools from the 19 participating countries
- O. Individuals who became recipients/laureates of The Rizal Prize or any other international recognized awards
- P. Main directors from the boards of non-government/non-profit organizations from the 19 participating countries

The following are unqualified to be nominators:

- A. Members of political parties
- B. Retired politicians
- C. Any representation, citizen or member of any organization from non-participating countries
- D. Members of The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee, serving, dismissed or retired
- E. The Supreme Council and the Council of Elders of the Order of the Knights of Rizal
- F. Individuals with criminal or civil violations
- G. Citizens and organizations from internationally sanctioned countries

Nominations

Nominees must be:

- Someone who directly works in creating positive change and measurable impact in his/her/their field. The achievement/s must inspire others.
- Respected professionals from their fields.
- Exhibiting justifications that the individual goes beyond their responsibilities and limitations.
- Collaborators of their governments, academic institutions, communities, and institutions.
- Showcasing exceptional leadership qualities.
- Model and law-abiding citizens of the 19 participating countries.

Nominees cannot be:

- Past or serving politicians, government officials, and members of the jury (The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee)
- Self-nominated
- Paid executives and board members of corporations and NGOs
- Awareness campaigners
- Organizers of meetings or any gatherings
- Dead individuals
- A nominee for The Prize for more than one category. Multiple nominations for a single individual/entity are unnecessary. The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee will choose the final category of nomination.
- Individuals with pending legal cases.

V. The Prize

Each Laureate will be admitted as a fellow to The Rizal Academy for Innovation and Leadership (TRAIL). The laureates can contribute as a teaching fellow or have the chance to showcase their projects. The Order of the Knights of Rizal and its affiliate organizations can also issue honorary knighthoods or memberships. This will grow the membership.

(The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Medallion Mock Up – Bano, Dexter Jr., P., March 8, 2023)

VI. Timeline of the Selection Process

- **March** - *The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee will send invitations to nominate.* They will provide a formal announcement and a letter addressed to the eligible nominators. Those who wish to get invitations can write to The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee as long as they are considered as eligible nominators. Official press release will not be provided to promote exclusivity and prestige.
- **August** – *Deadline for submission.* The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee can only accept nominations on or before the 16th of August. This date is the anniversary of the Rizal Act that took effect on August 16, 1956. Nominations received after the deadline will not be included. All nominations will be kept inside a vault. The vault will only be accessible through the two appointed members of The Committee also called as “**The Keyholders.**”
- **September to January** - *Due diligence and shortlisting.* The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Committee will do assessments and investigations on the nominations and the corresponding works presented. The shortlist and all the pertinent files will then be kept in a vault. The Keyholders will ensure that the shortlisted files will be sorted/separated from the rest.
- **February to March** – *Final Committee reading.* Only The Keyholders from the vault will retrieve the files. Arguments, discussions, and debates will be encouraged within The Committee during this timespan.
- **April** – *The Committee will vote for the Rizal Prize laureates.* For the first five (5) days, the laureates will be selected via majority vote. The sixth and seventh day will be for discussing and appealing if justified to be necessary. The first five (5) days of the second week should be for the conclusion of the selection process and The Committee must achieve at least fifty-one (51%) votes for the conferment of the laureates. The Final list of laureates will then be sealed in a brown envelope with a label, “*Hodie Rizal honoramus. Hodie eum adoramus*” which translates to “Today we honor Rizal. Today we adore him.”

The Keyholders will place the envelope inside the vault and retrieve the other files and nominations. The Keyholders will then close/lock the vault containing only the envelope. After this, they will completely destroy the other files and nominations. After this process, there will be a simultaneous official global press release at 7 A.M. PHST that contains the announcement of the names of The Rizal Prize Laureates that indicates their specific award/category. The same announcement in print will also be posted on all entryways of the International Headquarters of the Order of the Knights of Rizal and all of its chapters worldwide.

- **June 19** – *The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize Laureates will be bestowed through an award ceremony.* The Dr. Jose Rizal Prize will take place in Dapitan City, Philippines or Calamba City, Philippines. The laureates will receive The Rizal

Prize medallion and certificate, an official appointment to be a fellow of The Rizal Academy for Innovation and Leadership, and a document stating the amount of grant.

VII. Sponsoring an Award

Any company, individual, and organization with capacity and in good standing can sponsor a specific category of The Rizal Prize. This comes with the following limitations:

- The award cannot be renamed
- The sponsors will only be recognized through media releases and publication materials
- The sponsor shall shoulder the total grant prize for the specific category which will then be awarded to the laureates
- During the announcement, the laureates will not be notified by The Committee about the award's sponsor
- During the award ceremony, the sponsors will be recognized collectively

VIII. The 35-Year Vow of Secrecy

To maintain the integrity and solemnity of the award, The Committee will only release the list of nominations after thirty-five (35) years. The list of nominees for 2023 will only be available to the public on the year 2058. The same rule applies every year. Considering that The Keyholders will destroy the files and documents of the submitted nominations, they should not be revealed to the nominees and to the general public within the 35-year period. The individuals involved in Operation Bagumbayan, The Standing Group, and The Committee will also be subject to thirty-five year rule of sworn confidentiality that covers their involvement, membership, the process, the selection, the candidates, and the nominations. Any unofficial release of nominees and other leaks will be considered, invalidated, and labelled as "speculation" even if the announcement came from a credible source.